

Robust Design of Active Systems - An Approach to Considering Disturbances within the Selection of Sensors

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Abstract

Uncertainty occurs in every phase of the product lifecycle, while the properties of the product and thus its corresponding behavior regarding influence parameters are mostly determined during the development phase. One goal of product development is therefore the systematic support of the development of robust products. To achieve this goal, uncertainty must be methodically identified, analyzed and finally controlled by purposeful operations. One way to control emerging uncertainty is the application of active systems, for example the application of a feed-forward controller within a machine to compensate for reduced stiffness compared to a regular machine. On the other side, the use of active-control-systems generally increases a system's complexity and creates additional uncertainty.

In order to handle these conflicting factors a methodical approach is presented within this paper that contains appropriate models, criteria and procedures to assess the inherent uncertainty of active/adaptive systems.

The information obtained can then be used to develop robust active-/adaptive-systems. The SFB 805 process model is based on the SADT model and is used to detect uncertainty along process chains. The uncertainty is allocated to the process and the influencing parameters resources, people, information and disturbances. In addition, for the investigation of active systems, interactions between process and product must be taken into consideration. Accordingly, the process model is extended with reference to Heidemann whereas the product model is designed similar to the model of technical systems according to Nordmann. The various model elements are designed as a modular kit and can be combined to consider particular product structures.

In order to evaluate the model a multi purpose machine and a free bending process supported by an adaptive feed-forward controller is being modeled. Hence, the sensor/controller-behavior considering the influence of disturbances is examined by using the list of normalised disturbances. The control of the occurring uncertainty finally takes place using a design catalogue for sensors enhanced about aspects of uncertainty, to support the designer at their selection.

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1. Introduction

Uncertainty exists when the process properties in technical systems cannot be determined completely and deviations of these properties arise. Uncertainty occurs in every phase of the product lifecycle; product properties and their corresponding response to influence parameters are mostly determined during the development phase. Because of this, it is possible that a product will not fulfil expectations and the customer cannot gain the required benefit.

In order to handle or avoid uncertainty, one goal of product development is systematic support of the product development process. It is possible to design robust products, which means uncertainty can be controlled. To achieve this, uncertainty has to be identified, analysed and controlled methodically using focused operations.

One way to control occurring uncertainty is to apply active systems. With the help of manipulated variables, active systems can influence the process and react to deviations. However, the use of active systems generally increases a system's complexity and creates additional uncertainty.

To seize the potential of active systems, there is a need for a methodology that can handle the resulting, additional uncertainty. The approach discussed in this paper aims to control the uncertainty that relates to sensors, which is part of the overall objective.

2. Methodical approach to analysing active systems

A methodical approach to analysing active controlled systems implies a model that is capable of displaying the technical system in the context of appearance. According to (VDI 2221, 1987) a model is an abstract representation that contains only purposeful elements for a certain task. The model presented in this paper is mainly characterized by a combination of existing process and product models designed to achieve the required properties. Even though the approach presented in this paper is used for the design of robust sensors, the model has been developed to be valid for every design task related to robust design or uncertainty analysis.

2.1 Modelling technical systems

The process model developed in the collaborative research center SFB 805 is used and meaningful enlarged by purposeful elements. The basic model is shown in Figure 1. The model is based on the structured analysis and design technique (the SADT Model developed by *SofTech*, 2014) by describing data flows between processes. It uses the descriptions of states before and after a process, as proposed in the process model of Heidemann (2001).

The SFB 805 process model focuses on the description and visualization of uncertainty in all states of the product lifecycle by a division into states, processes and influencing parameters. The process is realized by appliances during usage, e.g. forming, machining, assembly devices or the product (Eifler et al., 2011). The states before and after the process can be described using properties such as material, geometric or usage.

Figure 1. SFB 805 process model according to Eifler et al. (2011)

During the transformation from one state into another, the process is influenced by the influencing parameters disturbance, information, resources and user.

With the aim of modelling active systems, the appliance and its interactions with the process and the environment have to be analysed in more detail than the SFB 805 process model actually does, because active systems are able to affect the process by adapted working factors. Hence, the model is additionally required to be able to analyse the interactions between product and process. Therefore, separation of the appliance and the process is necessary, which is also realized in the Heidemann process model (Heidemann, 2001).

Analysing active systems, an adequate product model must be chosen that is capable of displaying the transfer behaviour of the appliance in terms of its functional parts, their interactions and the flows of material, energy and signals. For this purpose, the model of technical systems according to (Birkhofer, Nordmann, 2002) fits perfectly with the SFB 805 process model, because it already contains the separation between process and appliance, as mentioned above (Figure 2). The model is used to analyse mechatronic systems and is realized as a combination of common block diagrams used in control engineering and functional modelling, as in (Feldhusen, Grote, 2013). The available elements are storage, conduction, change, transmission, sensor and controller.

Figure 2. Model of technical systems according to Birkhofer & Nordmann (2002), as a combination of block diagram and function model according to Feldhusen & Grote (2013)

To adapt the model to the requirements of robust design tasks, these elements have to be adjusted to general purpose. To obtain detailed information, more elements than just the actuator are of interest. Therefore, the functional model kit elements proposed within this paper are Storage, Actuator, Transmitter, Sensor and Controller. The intended interactions between these elements are modelled as material, energy and signal flows.

To investigate active systems, the interactions between elements of the appliance, process and environment have to be considered. According to Kloberdanz (2009), interactions between objects can generally be modelled as arrows. Additionally, these arrows can be used to mark intended or unintended interactions by their inclination. Diagonal arrows mark an unintended interaction or influence; vertical or horizontal arrows mark intended interactions. This notation is transferred into the SFB 805 model of technical systems.

2.2 Extended SFB 805 model of technical systems

The proposed model contains a separated perspective on process, appliance and its interactions, a differentiated appliance model, and a detailed model of interactions and disturbances between user, resources and environment. Although disturbances and information are not depicted specifically, they can be considered through the interaction arrows shown in Figure 3. The example application of the model is shown in the following section.

Figure 3. Extended SFB 805 model of technical systems

3. Model of a flexible bending process on a multi-purpose machine

The extended SFB 805 process model derived above is applied to a manufacturing process and analyzed in this section. In the context of production engineering, a manufacturing process is the focus of the process model. Consequently, the appliance is the forming machine, e.g. a press. Before the sample process is described using the extended process model, the 3D servo press, which is used as the appliance, will be explained. Conventional presses have the disadvantage that they provide the required forces and stroke rates but cannot adjust to fluctuating process conditions. Whereas incremental forming machines often do not offer forces and performance for efficient mass production (Calmano et al., 2013). The 3D servo press described in the following section closes this gap.

3.1. Application of the 3D Servo Press

The 3D Servo Press is a multi-technology machine which performs a flexible ram motion with various degrees of freedom (DoF).

It combines a stroke-controlled mode, provided by servo motor driven screws, and a force-controlled mode, provided by servo drives in conjunction with a crank mechanism. For special applications like wobbling, a combination of both operating modes is possible. The three independent drive systems are arranged in a star-shape, with an offset of 120° , as presented in

Figure 4. Due to these drive mechanisms, the ram of the 3D Servo Press is able to perform a conventional vertical stroke, as well as two additional rotational DoFs φ_1 (pitch) and φ_2 (roll) (Groche et al., 2010b).

In addition to the DoF of the press ram, this option allows a supplement of flexibility in the manufacturing of work-pieces. A wide variety of new processes and combinations of processes can be developed, for example, a combined flexible blanking and rolling process (Groche et al., 2010b) or an orbital forming process (Groche et al., 2010a).

Figure 4. Prototype and lever system of the 3D Servo Press according to Avemann et al. (2014)

3.2. Process and tool concept of a flexible bending process

The 3D Servo Press and a special tool system serve as appliance to the flexible bending process. It produces a heat dissipater with individual bending angles of all four fingers. A star-shaped sheet metal blank is used as the semi-finished part. The blank is fixed on a clamping block, as displayed in Figure 5. The tool tip, which is driven by the 3D Servo Press via the tool system, bends the sheet metal by performing a vertical motion with the path length h (Avemann et al., 2014).

Figure 5. Three-dimensional and process view of the heat dissipater (Avemann et al., 2014)

The angle α_{act} that results after dismounting the part is dependent on the actual path length h_{act} and on the amount of spring of the material. Since the drive system and tool system deform

depends on the load, h_{act} is expected to be smaller than the set-point value h_{set} . In addition, the spring-back angle of the part depends on the fluctuating properties of the processed semi-finished part: mainly sheet thickness and material. As described in (Avemann et al., 2014) and (Calmano et al., 2013), these uncertainties are controlled by the application of an adaptive feed-forward controller. The following section analyses the process control algorithm in relation to the extended process model, with the aim of analysing which uncertainties are controlled by the system and which additional uncertainties arise from integration of the necessary components.

3.3. Analysis of the manufacturing process with the extended SFB 805 process model

Figure 6 displays the components of the appliance used for the bending process. The forming process is performed by the x-y-z motion of a tool tip, which is driven by the machine. The resulting forming force $F_{x,y,z}$ acts on the tool tip and is transmitted to the tool system and ram, which acts as a transmission system. The tool system's purpose is the transforming between the 3 DoFs of the tool tip (x, y, z) and the 3 DoFs of the ram tool centre point (TCP: z , *pitch*, *roll*). The ram is attached to three independent drive systems, each consisting of a lever system (transmission) with force (F_{z_i}) and position (z_i) measurement, and an electrical servo drive (actuator x_i) with a rotary angle sensor (x_i). The three drive systems are illustrated only once, denoted with the index i for clarity of the diagram. The actuators generating the drive motion x_i as well as the sensors measuring x_i are attached to the drive position controller. The input for the drive position controller is a vertical z-position z_{set} which has to be transformed to drive coordinates using kinematic relations. The machine position controller uses the measured position of the outputs of the lever system z_i to compensate the deformation of the lever system under the load F_{z_i} . The set-point tool path h_{set} is generated by the process controller, which is designed as an adaptive feed-forward controller. It makes use of the properties of the semi-finished parts, determined by a detection algorithm from force and position information F_{z_i} and z_i (Calmano et al., 2013).

Figure 6. Flexible bending process described using the extended process model

The iterative feed-forward controller has to predict the transmission behaviour of all components in the described drive system. Since a technological consideration and description of all components, which is necessary to analytically derive a model function, is complex and time-consuming, a linear approximation of the global behaviour of the machine, tool system and part is implemented. The model parameters of this approximated model are determined iteratively from recent experiments by linear regression of the relation between stroke h and resulting angle α_{act} . Thus, the geometric property of the product, α_{act} , has to be measured externally after the process. This offers the additional benefit of taking into account the fluctuations in the transmission behaviour of the machine and tool as well as in the spring-back behaviour of the part. Disturbances to the drive system and part can thus be controlled in an iterative process control. The advantages and shortcomings of this approach are discussed in the following section.

3.4 Advancement of the process control using in-line angle measurement

The process controller in the design described above predicts the necessary machine stroke h to produce the desired set-point angle α_{set} without detailed information about the actual tool tip position and the current bending angle $\alpha_{act}(t)$. Disturbances affecting the product properties can only be detected and controlled iteratively after the current part is manufactured and measured externally. For detailed monitoring during the process and part properties during the process, an in-line measurement of the current bending angle is aspired. However, there are severe challenges when integrating sensors into a forming process. Whereas forces and positions of the drive system are easy to acquire, the benefit of controlling the forming process is low. The actual properties of the part on the other side are highly interesting for process control but are usually difficult to measure (Calmano et al., 2013).

In the presented bending process, the current bending angle $\alpha_{act}(t)$ could be measured by implementing machine vision cameras, for example. This measuring system consists of components additional to the components described in Figure 6: the camera as a sensor and a controller with implemented algorithms for image processing and analysis. All additional components are affected by disturbances, leading to additional uncertainties in the overall process. In order to minimize global system uncertainty, the benefits and disturbances caused by additional sensors have to be balanced. The analysis of sensors and measuring uncertainty, as described in Section 4, is part of this.

4. Design of robust sensors

To control uncertainty, especially in sensors, first, the additional uncertainty caused by these elements has to be analysed.

In the second step, the information is used to create a particular design catalogue to support the designer during the development process of appliances containing sensors. The catalogue includes diverse measurands and measuring principles related to its behaviour under particular disturbances. Finally, the benefit of the approach is shown using the model of the bending process presented in Section 3.

4.1 Additional uncertainty caused by sensors

The transmission of the measurand into a signal is subject to errors and is therefore a source of additional uncertainty (Figure 8). Some of the reasons are:

- **Measuring range**

The implemented measuring range of the sensor has to generally fit with the range of the measurand in order to be acquired. Deviations of the measurand that exceed the measuring range can cause unstable system behaviour.

- **Measuring resolution**

Changes of the measuring variable may result in transmitting errors if the sampling rate of the measuring system is not high enough. According to the Shannon Theorem, the sampling rate must be at least double the highest frequency of the measurand. In practical applications, normally the resolution frequency is up to 10 times higher than the measurand frequency (Nordmann, 2005). This is a heuristic rule to control uncertainty.

- **Influencing parameters**

Deviations in disturbances have a big influence on active systems. They affect the input measurand, the output signal, the transmitting behaviour or any combination of the three. Therefore, one of the key factors in controlling additional uncertainty in active systems is to design them to be resilient against these impacts.

4.2 Design catalogue for robust sensors

According to Mathias et al. (2010), there are three purposeful robust design (RD) principles to control deviations in influencing parameters. *These principles are eliminate disturbance, eliminate influence and eliminate impact.*

In order to design robust sensors, a design catalogue containing particular information about sensors and their behaviours, depending on disturbances can support application of these robust design principles (Figure 7). It closes the gap between general robust design rules and very detailed, specific information the designer gets from the manufacturers of sensors and therefore supports the design process. The information presented in the catalogue is based on intense literature research. The structure of the catalogue is related to the structure recommended by Roth (1982). He proposes a particular order to systematically access information during the design phase, which builds the structural frame for the catalogue. Future work will focus on a database approach to performing search operations more efficiently.

In order to apply the presented catalogue, the following procedure has to be executed by the designer:

The first part of the catalogue contains the measurand and the measuring principles so the designer chooses a measurand and, based on this information, obtains access to related information about the sensors, their properties and their sensitivity to disturbances. In addition, the catalogue provides some measures to eliminate the influence of the disturbances (which is not included in the depiction of the catalogue in this paper).

The designer can use the checklist of disturbances in (Mathias, 2012) to determine the disturbances occurring in a certain environment. Using this information, the designer can now choose an appropriate sensor for the situation.

Since the robust design principle *eliminate disturbance* should be avoided (Mathias, et al., 2010), the measures given in the catalogue focus on the principles *eliminate influence*, for example, protection against electromagnetic fields, and *eliminate impact*, for example, recalibration of the system.

measurand	measuring principle	sensor	measuring range	measuring resolution	No.	influence of disturbances				
						Temperature change	(electro-) magnetic field	humidity	vibration	dust and dirt accumulation
1	2	1	2	3		1	2	3	4	5
distance	magnetostrictive	magnetostrictive transducer	25-8000 mm	> 1 μ m	1	●	●	●	●	●
	magnetoresistive	digital ruler	< 100 000 mm	> 2,5 μ m	2	●	●	●	●	●
	resistive	(conductive plastic) potentiometer	< 4 000 mm	> 1 μ m	3	●	●	●	●	●
force	piezo-electric	piezo-electric force sensor	50 N – 1,2 MN	> 0,5 mN	4	●	●	●	●	●
	resistive	strain gauge (SGS) force sensor	1 N - 10 MN	> 0,4 mN	5	●	●	●	●	●

legend: ● no influence ● marginal influence ● strong influence

Figure 7. Example depiction of the design catalogue for robust sensors.

4.3 Example application of the design catalogue

The model of the flexible bending process shown in Figure 5 contains 2 different types of sensors. At the actuator and the lever system there are distance sensors, while at the lever system forces are also measured. A third type of sensor is outside of the investigated system and is used to measure the bending angle after the process. This information is used to close the control loop by adapting the feed-forward controller.

Since the product (3D servo press) already exists in this setup, the application of the catalogue has to be executed in inverse. The information is accessed through the type of the sensor instead of the type of measurand. Based on the type of sensor, the disturbances and their influence can be determined.

In order to demonstrate the procedure, the distance sensor of the lever system is investigated. The sensor is a magnetostrictive transducer with a measuring range of 10mm and a measuring resolution of 10 μ m. The catalogue shows it is strongly influenced by magnetic fields and marginal influence by temperature change and dirt accumulation (Figure 8). This information can now be used to predict the system behaviour in several environments and to design particularly robust solutions using the robust design principles.

Assuming that in a demonstration strong temperature changes occur, a possible solution for the principle *eliminate impact* could be an adequate and easy-to-use calibrating system. The principle *eliminate influence* could lead to a reflecting coating. The third principle, *eliminate disturbance*, could, for example, lead to a capsuled 3D servo press with an air-conditioning system. If no solution can be found, the catalogue can be used to choose alternatives, using the procedure mentioned in Section 4.3.

The same procedure can now be applied for the inline–angle measurement presented in section 3.4. to demonstrate its additional value.

5. Conclusion

The approach presented in this paper demonstrates that complex technical systems can be modelled, using the extended SFB 805 model of technical systems, to identify and analyse uncertainty. The model explicitly combines the executed process with the appliance and is therefore capable of being used to investigate interactions between them. The appliance model focuses on the main elements of active systems. Additionally, the interactions between a technical system and its environment can be modelled, while the consideration of disturbances is especially important to robust design tasks.

The design catalogue presented in Section 4 is an approach to closing the gap between general information about measurement principles and detailed information about specific sensors given by manufacturers. It contains information about sensor measurands, measurement principles and qualitative information about sensitivity to particular disturbances. It can be used to design robust products through the selection of sensors that are not sensitive to disturbance, or to adapt to new circumstances. For these purposes, the SFB 805 process model provides the necessary information.

Future work should have the objective of validating the model in practical design tasks. Additionally, the RD approach should be enhanced to control uncertainty of active systems in general, including controller and peripheral equipment.

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